

Tensammetric Studies of Organic Compounds with Reference to their Structural Influence on Surface Activity

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The surface activity of a series of closely related organic compounds, exhibiting tensammetric peaks, has been compared. From the study of the functional groups of organic compounds, the surface activity has been found to increase in the order: CHO > NH₂ > COOH > OH. The peak potential also shifts to more cathodic values in the same order. Ethers (aliphatic or aromatic) are more surface-active than corresponding alcohols and phenols. In the position isomers, surface activity follows the order: *ortho* > *meta* > *para* and peak potentials are independent of the position of the substituent groups. The surface activity is greater when functional group is attached to the nucleus as compared to when it is attached to the side chain. Further, the surface activity decreases with increase in the number of substituent groups in the organic compounds.

Gupta and Sharma¹ have shown that tensammetry can be successfully used to assess the structural influence on the surface activity of various aliphatic alcohols. The present investigation records a comparative study, showing the surface activity of a series of closely related organic compounds, known to provide tensammetric peaks.

EXPERIMENTAL

Organic solid compounds used were either of B. D. H. or Merck's quality and were recrystallised before use. Organic liquid compounds were also extra pure samples of either B.D.H. or Merck's quality and were redistilled in all-glass fractionating column and the middle one-thirds of the distillates were used for the experiments. The mercury used for the pool electrode and dropping electrode was passed through Meyer's column, washed several times with distilled water, dried, passed through a sintered-glass filter, and finally distilled under vacuum.

The apparatus employed in the present investigation was the same as that described earlier²⁻³, the only modification being as much reduction as possible of series resistance. This was done by applying to a d.m.e. a 50 c/sec. a.c. ripple of ± 40 mV (r.m.s.) over the d.c. potentials and observing the alternating component of the resulting pulsating current. As the capacitative impedance of the d.m.e. was much higher than the rest of the impedance of the system, the magnitude of the alternating current provided a measure of the d.m.e. capacity. The d.c. potentials have been expressed with reference to the saturated calomel electrode. The constants of the dropping mercury electrode were: $m = 4.564$ mg./sec., $t = 1.8$ sec. per drop in 0.1M-KCl (open circuit).

1. *Kolloid Z.*, 1963, **190**, 40.

2. Doss and Sundaram, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, **35A**, 27.

3. Doss and Gupta, *ibid.*, 1952, **36A**, 493.

Procedure.—0.1 Molar potassium chloride (B.D.H., A.R.) solution was used as the indifferent electrolyte and was invariably shaken and kept in contact with mercury and mercurous chloride. In each case, the measurements were taken with the indifferent electrolyte. The effect of organic compounds has been expressed in terms of the percentage increase (with sign) of the alternating current, which provides practically the percentage increase in the average differential capacity. The dropping mercury electrode was cathodic throughout the measurements. All the experiments were done at a pH of 10.8 and at a temperature of $20^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$.

TABLE I

Magnitudes and peak potentials of organic compounds.

Compounds.	Conc.	%A.C.	Peak potential.
Benzylamine	1.0 %	222.0 μ A	—1.45 V
Phenylacetic acid	1.0	214.3	—1.45
Benzyl alcohol	1.0	204.0	—1.32
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	1.0	100.0	—1.20
<i>n</i> -Butanol	1.0 } 5.0 }	94.0 } 216.3 }	—1.26 } —1.35 }
Anisol	Satd.	242.2	—1.27
Diethyl ether	5.0	238.2	—1.38
Guaiacol	1.0	212.0	—1.45
<i>o</i> -Cresol	1.0	236.0	—1.28
<i>m</i> -Cresol	1.0	219.5	—1.28
<i>p</i> -Cresol	1.0	206.8	—1.28
Catechol	1.0	68.3	—1.05
Resorcinol	1.0	63.3	—1.05
Hydroquinone	1.0	59.4	—1.05
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.2	83.3	—1.19
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.2	78.0	—1.19
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.2	68.8	—1.19
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	0.2	44.5	—1.17

For comparing surface activity between various surface-active substances, either the depression of the differential capacity at about electro-capillary zero was used or the desorption peak at potentials away from electro-capillary zero. As the capacity minimum was not sharp and was sometimes flat over a considerable range of potentials, the comparison became difficult and therefore the magnitude of the desorption peak was used for comparing the surface activity of various organic compounds.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Functional Groups.—Fig. 1 shows the effect of similar organic compounds with -CHO, -NH₂, -COOH, and -OH (phenolic) as functional groups on the differential capacity of the double layer. The concentration of all the organic compounds was kept constant and the magnitudes of the desorption peaks were compared. The surface activity

thus increases in the order: $\text{PhCHO} > \text{PhNH}_2 > \text{PhCOOH} > \text{PhOH}$. The peak potentials also shift to more cathodic values in the same order. It has been shown earlier⁴ that benzaldehyde exhibits tensammetric peak at alkaline pH. The fact that the magnitude of the benzaldehyde peak is very large, as compared to other compounds of the series, may be due to its reaction with NaOH and formation of the products which are surface-active. These results are further supported by the study of the compounds, viz., benzylamine, phenylacetic acid, and benzyl alcohol as well as *n*-butylamine and *n*-butanol, as shown in Table I. Similarly anisol, diethyl ether, and guaiacol (catechol ether) are more surface-active than benzyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, and catechol respectively (vide Table I). The peak potentials do not show any regular behaviour; this may be due to the shift of the electro-capillary zero to different extents by these compounds.

FIG. 1

1. 0.2% Benzaldehyde.
2. 0.2% Aniline.
3. 0.2% Benzoic acid.
4. 0.2% Phenol.

Effect of Position Isomers.—Fig. 2 shows the effect of various isomers of toluidine on the capacity of the mercury-aqueous interface. The surface activity of the compounds depends on the position of the substituent groups. The surface activity follows the order: *ortho* > *meta* > *para*. This fact is further confirmed by observations of the effect of cresols, dihydroxybenzenes (catechol, resorcinol, and hydroquinone), and hydroxybenzoic acid (vide Table I). The peak potentials are independent of the position of the substituent groups.

Effect of Position of Functional Groups.
—Fig. 3 shows the effect of position of -OH and -NH₂ groups on the surface activity of benzyl alcohol and *o*-cresol as well as benzylamine and *o*-toluidine respectively. It can be seen that surface activity is greater when functional group is attached to the nucleus as compared to when it is attached to the side chain having the same number of carbon atoms. The peak

FIG. 2

1. 0.6% *o*-Toluidine.
2. 0.6% *m*-Toluidine.
3. 0.6% *p*-Toluidine.

potential is less negative when functional group is attached to the nucleus than that when it is attached to the side chain.

Effect of Increase of -OH(phenolic) and -NH₂ Groups.—Fig. 4 shows the effect of increase of hydroxyl groups on the surface activity of phenolic acids. *o*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (salicylic acid), which is monohydroxy, is found to be more surface-active than dihydroxy, i.e., 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid and the dihydroxy acid is more surface-active than trihydroxy, i.e. 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid (gallic acid) containing the same number of carbon atoms as in monohydroxy- and dihydroxy-benzoic acids. The peak potential of the phenolic acids shifts to less negative values in the order: trihydroxy > dihydroxy > monohydroxy-benzoic acids.

FIG. 3

1. 1.0% *o*-Cresol.
2. 1.0% Benzyl alcohol.
3. 0.2% *o*-Toluidine.
4. 0.2% Benzylamine.

FIG. 4

1. 0.2% *o*-Hydroxybenzoic acid.
2. 0.2% 2,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid.
3. 0.2% 3,4,5-Trihydroxybenzoic acid.

Similarly, aniline is seen to be more surface-active than *p*-phenylenediamine containing two -NH₂ groups in *para* position, having the same number of carbon atoms (Table F). The peak potential of aniline is less negative than that of *p*-phenylenediamine.

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